
Impact of Corruption on Corporate Payout Policy: Evidence from selected MENA Countries

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of corruption on payout policy in light of the agency theory in seven selected MENA countries. The main dataset used in the analysis is up to 5,684 firm– year observations for 435 non-financial firms listed on the stock exchanges of the seven MENA countries for 20 years (2002-2021). This study uses regression models as logistic regression and weighted least square (WLS). The study finds that perceived corruption is positively related to both the decision to pay dividends and the payout ratio. These findings imply that when corruption is more severe, firms are more likely to distribute dividends and, the payout ratios tend to be higher. To the best of the Author’s knowledge, this is a first attempt to test the influence of corruption on corporate pay out policy within the context of the MENA region.

Keywords: *Corruption, agency problem, MENA region, Dividend policy*

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1. Introduction

Corruption has received an immense amount of attention in recent literature; it is no stranger to the world today. Almost all countries have signs of its existence. As noted by Tran (2020, p. 1) “*Corruption has become one of the most problematic issues in the real world and the academic world*”. The impact of corruption on the macroeconomic aggregates (e.g., economic growth, investment, political instability and human capital) has been debatable and literature is divided into two broad views. One view, considers corruption a hindrance to economic growth and development, acting as “sand in the wheels” (Mauro, 1995; Blackburna, et al., 2006). Conversely, the second part of the literature view that corruption, under certain conditions can promote development by “greasing the wheels” as it helps to foster growth of the economic aggregate (Lui, 1985).

Despite extensive research on corruption at the macroeconomic level, firm-level studies remain relatively scarce. As mentioned by Wei (2001, p. 11) “*Firm level studies are generally rare, for the obvious reason that firm-level data are more difficult to assemble*”. Nevertheless, corruption has a profound impact on the institutional environment in which firms operate. According to the World Bank’s Enterprise Surveys, approximately 14.9% of firms worldwide have encountered bribery, with at least one instance of a public official requesting a bribe¹. Moreover, corruption poses a more significant threat to business operations than even terrorism (Lemma , 2015). Even while corruption is widespread in firms, surprisingly little is known about how it impacts firms and their policies. Donadelli (2014) suggests that at firm level, corruption exacerbates agency conflicts between managers and shareholders, which in turn may have influence on corporate policies.

Dividend policy is one of the most debated topics in corporate finance. While numerous studies have examined the determinants of corporate dividend policy, focusing primarily on

¹ <https://www.enterprisesurveys.org/>

firm-specific characteristics (Mitton, 2004). Relatively few have explored the influence of institutional factors, particularly corruption, on corporate decisions. In specific, the impact of corruption on the dividend policy is still up for debate.

This study contributes to the literature by investigating how corruption affects dividend policy across the MENA countries in light of the agency problem mechanism. The MENA region is widely perceived as highly corrupt, with persistently low rankings on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) (Haykal, 2017). Amid growing demands for transparency and accountability, understanding how corruption affects corporate decisions is increasingly important.

This study argues that corruption exacerbates the agency problem by increasing the agency cost of equity. Managers, who are responsible for overseeing daily business operations, may exploit firm resources to pay bribes to public officials for personal gain, thereby fostering direct ties with corrupt government entities. In some cases, they may also engage in corrupt practices to secure short-term advantages for the company. Consequently, shareholders have strong incentives to closely monitor managerial behavior and pressure them to distribute higher dividends as a strategy to mitigate the agency problem.

1.1. Problem Statement

"The more we look at the dividend picture, the more it seems like a puzzle, with pieces that just do not fit together" (Black, 1976, p. 5). The discussion of dividend policies is still quite interesting. Numerous studies have investigated the factors influencing a firm's dividend policy and it is one of the significant concerns that are being explored in great detail in empirical research, however there is still no consensus on dividend pay-out decisions. It is important to emphasize that external variables, in addition to internal ones, have a considerable impact on dividend policy (Jensen & Johnson, 1995; Jensen & Smith, 2000). Investment opportunity, profitability, and liquidity are examples of internal elements, but macroeconomic issues including growth, stability, technological progress, and shifts in consumer preferences are the most significant external determinants, according to Roberto (2002). Very limited papers addressed the impact of corruption on the decision to pay dividends and they were limited to the international sample (Tran, 2020; Tran, 2021) and to our knowledge no papers examined the impact of corruption on the decision to pay dividends in selected MENA countries.

On another side, corruption is a widespread phenomenon almost existing in majority of the countries. The existing literature on the "economics of corruption" is biased towards looking

at the connections between corruption and economic aggregates. Various empirical studies analyzes corruption on varied range of macro issues namely economic growth (Mauro, 1995; Ghalwash , 2014; Huang, 2016), health care and education services, (Gupta, et al., 2000) foreign direct investment (CUERVO-CAZURRA , 2006). Although studies of this nature are important to assess the impact of corruption on the economic aggregates and improve our compression of the cost of corruption to society, but they do not take into account the impact of corruption on the firm level.

Recent research has seen a modest but rising thread of studies addressing the relationship between corruption and firm level decisions, which appears to be a reaction to this constraint. This branch of the literature to the best of our knowledge consists of Asiedu and Freeman (2009), Javorcik and Wei (2009) on the impact of corruption on the firm-level investment. In similar spirit, Fisman and Svensson, (2007) and Nguyen and Dijik (2012) investigate the effect of corruption on firm growth. Rather recently, Thakura and Kannadhasan (2019) and Tran (2020) examine the effect of corruption and corporate cash holdings and conclude that corruption is positively associated with the cash holdings. Moreover, Donadelli (2014) finds that at the firm level, agency problems are worsened in corruption sensitive industries. Although Hossaina et al. (2019) and Tran (2020) offered empirical evidence and newly, Tran (2021) finds that local corruption in Vietnam has positive effect on both the likelihood to pay dividends and payout ratio. Still, further study is needed to better understand how corruption impacts the dividend policy, especially that the previous findings are only limited on a sample of worldwide countries, over and above that, the disruption that corruption causes to firms is demonstrated as a more dangerous threat to firm operations than terrorism (Lemma , 2015). We have little knowledge on the impact of corruption on the corporate dividend policy in the MENA region, considering that we note that corruption has been exacerbating in the MENA countries. According to the Global Peace Index 2023, the Middle East and North Africa region continues to be the least peaceful region in the world for the ninth year in a row (Institute for Economics & Peace, 2023). To the best of our knowledge, no study has been conducted on the effect of corruption on the decision to pay dividends for the firms operating in the MENA region, so it is imperative to investigate how corruption influences dividend decisions at the firm-level in the context of the MENA region.

This study aims at filling this void by investigating whether the perceived corruption in the MENA region impacts the decision to pay dividends or not.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Corruption has been a critical topic over the past two decades; there has been escalating academic articles being published on this subject (Jain, 2001). Moreover, the discussion related to corruption has been high on the agendas of the international organizations, including the International Monetary Fund, World Trade Organization and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (Sandholtz & Koetzle, 2000). According to the United Nations Secretary-General Antonio Guterres message for International Anti-Corruption Day (held every year on December 9th): *“Corruption is criminal, immoral and the ultimate betrayal of public trust. It is even more damaging in times of crisis – as the world is experiencing now with the COVID-19 pandemic. The response to the virus is creating new opportunities to exploit weak oversight and inadequate transparency, diverting funds away from people in their hour of greatest need”* (United Nations , 2020)

The definition of the corruption is challenging and there is no agreement on a working definition, as it is a multidisciplinary subject that scholars from different fields have examined including law, finance, economics, accounting and even international business. (Lemma , 2015). Corruption, defined by the Transparency International is *“the abuse of entrusted power for private gain “* (Transparency International, 2020). Measuring corruption is difficult, especially that it is hidden, hard to tackle and always carried out away from the public eyes (Jain, 2001). The principal approach to measuring corruption has been based on perception indexes built upon expert or public opinion (Mauro, 1995). Measuring corruption by assessing how societies perceive it, became recognized as a valid method. Especially when employing the transparency International Corruption Perception Index and the governance indicators of the World Bank, which are acknowledged as the most two commonly used hybrid measures of corruption (Knack, 2007; Asiedu & Freem, 2009).

There are two broad viewpoints regarding the impact of corruption on economic growth: the “grease in the wheels” stance vs. the “sand in the wheels” standpoint.

The “grease in the wheels” belief suggests that corruption has the potential to improve growth; by this means it is viewed as the lubricant to grease the stiff wheels of rigid government administration (Nathaniel, 1964). Lui (1985) argue that corruption can be a way to speed up the bureaucratic process. The most cited example is the “speed money” paid by individuals to shorten the strict procedures. Dreher & Gassebner (2013) find that corruption reduces the negative impact of regulations on entrepreneurship in highly regulated economies. Another

study maintains the view that corruption in Asian countries as China and South Korea stimulates the increase of economic aggregate (Huang, 2016). Wang (2016) points out that since investment is one of the main driving forces in China's economic growth, the impact of anti-corruption on investment would result in the decline of economic growth.

The other side maintains that corruption leads to dampening the economic growth and development. Mauro (1995) argues that corruption has a negative relationship with investment, which leads to lowering the economic growth. Ghalwash (2014) finds that corruption negatively impacts economic growth in Egypt. Other studies suggest that corruption increases the size of the unofficial economy (Friedmana et al., 2000). Hakimi & Hamdi (2015) concludes that corruption is a serious hurdle to economic growth in MENA countries since it affects investment activities and foreign direct investment inflows. In this view, it is suggested that corruption is the "sand" in the wheels of development.

Several prior studies have focused on the impact of corruption at the macro level and very few studies examine its impact at the micro level (Donadelli et al., 2014). The scarcity of research has been noted by Svensson (2003, p. 209) who wrote, "*Despite more than two decades of research, however, economic studies on corruption at the firm level are rather limited*". In line with the scant results investigating the relationship between corruption and firm level decisions, the relationship between the corruption and the corporate dividend policy in light of the agency theory is examined. The agency problem as recognized by Jensen & Mecklings (1976), relies on the separation between ownership of resources and the right to control resources in companies. Broadly, there are two types for the agency problems (Tran, 2019). The first type results from the conflicts of interests occurring between the shareholders (principals) and the managers (agents). The shareholders' main goal is to maximize their return from investment and thereby maximizing owner's wealth, while the main aim for the managers is to (1) maximize their profit; (2) sustain their position; and (3) reap personal benefits (Donadelli et al., 2014). Consequently, agency costs arise because of the imperfection of the principal-agency relationship in a company (Putra et al., 2018). According to Jensen & Mecklings (1976) agency costs are expenditures that result in lowering the welfare of the shareholders; they are the sum of monitoring expenditures (undertaken by principals), bonding costs (undertaken by the agent) and residual costs (the reduction in the value of the firm due to the presence of a principal-agent relationship). Managers' duty in the company is to control, run the firm and make decisions. Amidst a corrupted environment, they are greatly exposed to offering bribes in order to obtain business opportunities and speed up the rigid process (grease

the wheels). Moreover, bribery could be useful for their short-term goals since it may allow a manager to temporarily hide his failure to enhance the value of the company. In both scenarios (corruption to the benefit of the company and to the benefit of the manager), corruption imposes agency costs to the firm. In other words, in participating in corruption, managers act following their own interests and not pursuing those of the shareholders, creating a misalignment of interests. Aligning to this point, recently it is been found that corruption is positively related to cash holdings (Tran, 2020). Hereby, in a corrupted environment, shareholders have high incentives to force managers to pay dividends as a mechanism to reduce agency costs and to limit the excessive cash, which managers can use to pursue their short-term goals. This leads to formulating the following hypothesis:

H1. Corruption has a significant positive impact on the decision to pay dividends and the dividend payout ratio.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research methods

The key purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of corruption on the decision to pay dividends and the dividend pay-out ratio in seven selected countries in the MENA region. This study integrates predictive analysis. This technique enables the researcher to identify and explain patterns or relationships within the data. (Hoang & Watson, 2022). Therefore, it provides insights into the impact of corruption on payout policy in the selected MENA countries. Predictive analytics include classification techniques as regression techniques (Rodrigues, et al., 2021). Hence this study employs the logistic regression and weighted least squares, to model the relationships between variables. As such, the research design aligns with the explanatory purpose of uncovering cause-effect dynamics while using predictive models to assess and quantify relationships.

3.2. Research Models

A binary logistic regression model is used in this study and will be conducted using SPSS. This model is used when the dependent variable is dichotomous or binary. Since it leads to a simple interpretation, the categories are typically labelled as "0" and "1" (Changpetch, 2023). The dependent variable which is the decision to pay dividends has a dichotomous outcome where if the firm does not pay dividends, a value of "0" is assigned and if the firm pays, a value of "1" is assigned. Moreover, the Weighted Least Squares regression (WLS) model is employed. The main advantage of the WLS is its ability to handle regression scenarios where

the data points are of different quality and this is considered as the primary benefit when compared to alternative techniques (O. , 2015). The model weights the observations proportional to the reciprocal of the error variance for that observation and so overcomes the issue of non-constant variance.

The regression models are as follows:

$$\mathbf{DTP} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{PRO} + \beta_2 \text{CAH} + \beta_3 \text{FGR} + \beta_4 \text{LEV} + \beta_5 \text{SIZ} + \beta_6 \text{ATG} + \beta_7 \text{REA} + \beta_8 \text{SSA} + \beta_9 \text{COI} + \beta_{10} \text{PMI} + \beta_{11} \text{GCI} + \beta_{12} \text{EGR} + \beta_{13} \text{UAC} + \varepsilon$$

Equation 1

$$\mathbf{DPR} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{PRO} + \beta_2 \text{CAH} + \beta_3 \text{FGR} + \beta_4 \text{LEV} + \beta_5 \text{SIZ} + \beta_6 \text{ATG} + \beta_7 \text{REA} + \beta_8 \text{SSA} + \beta_9 \text{COI} + \beta_{10} \text{PMI} + \beta_{11} \text{GCI} + \beta_{12} \text{EGR} + \beta_{13} \text{UAC} + \varepsilon$$

Equation 2

Where DTP is the decision to pay dividends. It is measured as a dummy variable, so it is equal to one if the company distributed dividends on that year and zero otherwise (Riyanti & Yulianto, 2018; Trabelsi, et al., 2019). DPR is dividend pay-out ratio measured by total cash dividends scaled by net sales. It is suggested to use net sales as a deflator instead of earnings to calculate pay-out ratio since low earnings will make the ratio unstable (Tran, 2020; Tembo & Chipeta, 2024). COI is Corruption index and independent variable. Corruption Perception Index (CPI) is used which is annually provided by Transparency International as the main proxy for corruption. CPI ranks countries by “their perceived levels of public sector corruption” according to opinion surveys, which are submitted by experts and business people. Control Variables is divided into firm specific variables and country variables. The Firm-level variables employed in this research are found to affect corporate dividend policy in many prior studies. These include PRO, profitability is among the most crucial variables that determine dividend payment. One ratio that is frequently used to gauge profitability is return on assets (ROA) (Ahmed, 2018; Abdullah & Tursoy, 2021; GADOIU, 2014). CAH is Cash, there is debate on the impact of cash on dividend policy. According to DeAngelo et al., (2006), it is unclear how cash holdings affect company payout policies. Since businesses of varying sizes have been noticed, the ratio of cash by dividing the cash balance to total assets is being used (Xu & Li, 2018). FGR is firm growth, it is reported that a growing firm has less to pay as dividends and

therefore, bear a negative relationship (Mitton , 2004). The firm growth is measured by the growth in total assets for each year (Rahman, et al., 2015). LEV, is leverage, it is another important consideration when deciding on a dividend policy; it indicates the level of debt in a company. Firm debt ratio is said to be one of the primary factors influencing a company's decision to pay dividends (Amidu & Abor, 2006). SIZ is size, Company's size is one of the factors that need to be taken into consideration in dividend policy. Applying the natural log of total assets to measure a firm's size is more relevant because it accounts for the effects of scale economies market power related to a firm's size. It has a higher stability level than other proxies, and is more likely to last over time (Saraswati & Bernawati, 2020). ATG is asset tangibility, it may have an impact on dividend policy. Tangibility of the assets is measured by dividing the tangible assets by total assets (Rahman, et al., 2015). REA is Firm Maturity, According to DeAngelo (2006), mature enterprises have fewer investment opportunities accessible to them, which enable them to pay higher dividends. Thus, the mature companies pay dividends more often. To study the firm maturity, the ratio of retained earning deflated by the total assets is used. SSA is business uncertainty, The effect of uncertainty on dividend policy is controlled by using the five-year standard deviation of net sales to assets. As Wei (1997) notes, uncertainty, often caused by market volatility, economic fluctuations, and corruption, can significantly affect a firm's corporate decisions, particularly in the area of dividend policy.

As for the country specific variables employed in this research, they are found to affect corporate dividend policy in many prior studies. They include the shareholder protection, creditor protection, annual GDP growth rate and national culture and legal origin dummy. PMI, is protecting minority investors index representing the strength of minority shareholder protection, annually provided by the World Bank and it is based on the methodology of Djankova (2008). Research has found that corporate dividend policy is not only influenced by firm level characteristics, but as well the strength of the legal regime (shareholder and creditor rights) is a crucial factor to be considered when assessing the corporate dividend policy. GCI is Getting Credit indicator, representing creditor protection; annually provided by the World Bank. EGR is annual economic growth measured by the growth rate of Gross Domestic Product collected from the World Bank database. The gross domestic product growth rate serves as a gauge for the growth of the economy. Liu et al., (2018) assert that GDP has a positive impact on dividend policy is the Uncertainty Avoidance. It is the proxy used to measure culture in order to assess the impact of culture on the dividend policy provided by Hofstede (Hofstede, et al., 2010).

3.3. Research Data

Our empirical investigation is based on a sample of listed firms in the stock markets of 7 countries Egypt, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and UAE; all located in the MENA region. The sample will be covering the 2002-2021 financial period. Micro data is computed from the financials statements of the listed companies obtained from Bloomberg Database. As for the macro data for the 7 countries, it is obtained from the World Bank.

The main dataset used in regression analysis is up to 5,684 firm– year observations for 435 non-financial firms listed on the stock exchanges of the seven MENA countries. The data spans from 2002 to 2021(20 years), capturing variations in corporate decisions (including dividend pay-outs) across different economic and political environments in the region.

3.3.1. A Regional Overview

Corruption is pervasive in the majority of the MENA nations, and the majority of these nations are considered to have substantial corruption issues. Referring back to the relationship between corruption and the corporate payment decision, and in terms of the selection to the countries in the MENA region that our study is based on. The study is founded on the fact that the level of corruption varies from one country to another. Accordingly, 7 countries with varied corruption levels in the MENA region are chosen and segregated in to three groups according to the average score of the corruption perception index (CPI). Transparency International's CPI index is used to calculate the levels of corruption. The index scores 180 countries around the world by their perceived levels of public sector corruption on a scale from 0 (highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean) and then ranks the countries by their score; the country ranked first indicates a clean system and the low ranking indicates a high level of corruption. The average score is calculated from 2003 till 2021 since the CPI of year 2002 was not available for all countries except Egypt. Each of the seven sample countries fell into the below categories. Following the same method of Zouaoui et al (2017), the Hierarchical Classification Method is conducted, grouping the countries into High, Medium and low corrupt countries according to their average score in the years under study. High Corrupted Countries are those countries in which corruption is persistent and their average score is above 50, the intermediate corrupted countries are those which have score more than 40 and below than 50, lastly the low corrupted countries are those which are characterized with their good performance and their score are below 50. The constraint of data limits our sample to seven MENA countries: Egypt, Iraq, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the UAE.

Table 1. Hierarchical Classification Method

Level of Corruption	CPI Score	Countries
High	CPI < 40	- Iraq - Egypt
Intermediate	40 < CPI < 50	- Kuwait - KSA
Low	CPI > 50	- Oman - Qatar - UAE

4. Empirical Results

4.1. Descriptive Statistics

The total sample firms for each country are as follows: Egypt (43), Iraq (41), Kuwait (76), Oman (83), Qatar (21), Saudi Arabia (118) and UAE (53). Table 2 presents the number of sample firms and observations for each country. Among these countries, there is substantial heterogeneity in terms of corruption.

Table 2. Total Number of Firms and Observations in each Country

#	Country	No. of firms	No. of observations
1.	Egypt	43	626
2.	Iraq	41	294
3.	Kuwait	76	1,104
4.	Oman	83	1,131
5.	Qatar	21	289
6.	Saudi Arabia	118	1,538
7.	UAE	53	702
	Total	435	5,684

Table 3. Annual Number of firms Observations

<i>Year</i>	<i>N</i>								
2002	7	2006	274	2010	309	2014	361	2018	364
2003	65	2007	284	2011	326	2015	366	2019	357
2004	111	2008	295	2012	330	2016	359	2020	351
2005	231	2009	285	2013	336	2017	360	2021	313

Table 3, shows that the number of firms increases over the years, as the dataset starts in 2002 with just 7 observations and in 2018, it peaks to 364 observations. In 2021, the number drops to 313 observations since many firms are delisted under the impact of COVID-19, which disrupted business operations globally.

Table 4. Summary Result for the Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	N	Min	Max	Mean	STD
DTP	5684	.00	1.00	.43	.50
DPR	5684	.00	5.79	.11	.30
COI	5684	15	77	47.23	15.14
PRO	5684	-5.82	.76	.04	.17
CAH	5684	.00	1	.13	.15
FGR	5684	-.97	45.66	.13	1.03
LEV	5684	.00	7.92	.13	.25
SIZ	5684	5.43	22.13	12.82	2.70
ATG	5684	.00	1.14	.40	.27
REA	5684	-28.41	.96	.05	.84
SSA	5684	0	2	.16	.20
PMI	5684	28	86	55.10	12.28
CRI	5684	0	70	41.62	14.93
EGR	5684	-12.04	26.20	3.49	4.85
UAC	5684	55	96	70.03	10.95

Table 4 represents the description of the research sample. The independent variable in this study is the Corruption (COI) and its proxy is the corruption perception index presented in a score from 1 (Highly corrupt) to 100 (very clean) to each country under study. The minimum score of 15 corresponds to Iraq, which has one of the lowest CPI scores globally. This extremely low score suggests that corruption is widely perceived as a significant problem within the country. The maximum score of 77 corresponds to the Qatar. The standard deviation of 15 suggests that the level of corruption perception varies widely across the region and selected countries from clean environments in Qatar to more corrupt environment in Iraq.

Dependent variables are measured by two proxies. One is the Decision to Pay Dividends and its values are formulated into binary numbers, representing the numbers using only two digits, “0” and “1”. Zero represents the firms that do not pay dividends and number one represents the firms that pay dividends. Accordingly, the minimum value is zero and the maximum value is one. The mean value of 0.43 suggests that 43% of firms in the sample pay dividends, while 57% do not. The standard deviation of 0.50 indicates that the variable is fairly balanced between the two categories. Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) is the second proxy; the payout ratio is calculated by dividing cash dividends paid by the firms’ net sales. It is suggested to use net sales as a deflator instead of earnings to calculate pay-out ratio since low earnings will make the ratio unstable (Tran, 2020; Tembo & Chipeta, 2024). The minimum value of the dividend payout ratio is 0, indicating that some firms did not pay dividends at all. The maximum value is 5.79 suggesting that in rare cases firms pay more to its shareholders than the achieved sales. This was witnessed in Canal Shipping Agencies Company (CSAG.CA) based in Egypt. In 2021, the sales recorded 53M and the cash dividends recorded 312M, noting that in this year the company witnessed drop in its sales with 4%. The mean value is 0.11 indicating that, on average firms distribute 11 % of their net sales as dividends. The standard deviation is 0.30, which highlights considerable variability in dividend payout practices across the sample.

The descriptive statistics of the firm and country control variables in the MENA region from 2002 to 2021 reveal significant variations across key financial indicators, reflecting varied economic and institutional environments in the region. Profitability (PRO), measured by return on assets (ROA), exhibits a wide range, with some firms experiencing substantial losses, such as Saudi Industrial Financials in 2017, while others achieved strong returns, leading to an average ROA of 4%. Cash holdings (CAH) also vary considerably, with some firms operating without cash balances, whereas others, like Ikarus Petroleum located in Kuwait, held cash equal to their total assets in 2005. Firm growth (FGR), measured as the Annual Growth Rate of Total

Assets. The lowest growth rate is -0.97 indicating that some firms experienced a decline in total assets by up to 97% during the period. This was witnessed in Light Industries Company located in Iraq in 2013, noting that there were some notable factors that occurred at that time including political instability and economic and currency instability which led to liquidity issues that could impact company's asset management. The highest growth is 45 demonstrating that certain firms achieved extraordinary growth, expanding their assets base. Financial leverage (LEV), ratio that measures the extent assets company has been financed by debt. The lowest debt to total assets ratio is zero, indicating that some firms operate with no debt financing. These firms likely rely entirely in equity financing. The highest ratio is 7.92%, suggesting extreme levels of debt compared to assets in certain firms. Asset tangibility (ATG) measured by dividing the tangible assets by total assets. (Rahman, et al., 2015). This metric differs across industries, with capital-intensive firms like Al Suwadi Power which is engaged in the generation of electric power, a company that is heavily investing in its plants, whereas service-oriented firms hold fewer physical assets. Firm maturity (REA), measured by retained earnings deflated by total assets. The minimum ratio of -28.41 suggests that some firms in the sample have accumulated substantial losses relative to their total assets. The maximum ratio of 0.96 suggests that some firms have retained earnings that are almost equal to or slightly less than their total assets. This could indicate that the firm is highly profitable, with a large portion of its earnings being retained for reinvestment or to strengthen its financial position. Uncertainty (SSA) is the five-year standard deviation of net sales to assets. It is a measure of a firm's financial volatility, reflecting the uncertainty or variability in its sales relative to its total assets over a period of five years. The minimum SSA value of 0 indicates that for some firms, there has been no variation in their net sales relative to assets over the past five years. This suggests that these firms have experienced very stable or predictable sales performance compared to their total asset base. The maximum SSA value of 2 represents firms with high variability in net sales relative to their assets over the five-year period. The average SSA of 0.16 suggests that, on the whole, firms in the sample experience moderate stability in their net sales relative to total assets.

Country variables such as the Protecting Minority Investors (PMI) and Creditor Protection indices (GCI) indicate wide discrepancies across countries, with Qatar and Iraq showing weaker protections, while Saudi Arabia and the UAE demonstrate stronger regulatory frameworks. Annual GDP growth rates (EGR), also varies, with Iraq witnessing sharp contractions in 2020 due to external shocks, while Qatar experienced rapid expansion during

its infrastructure boom. Uncertainty Avoidance (UAC) scores highlight cultural differences, Egypt recorded the lowest score, which is 55, and Iraq recorded the maximum score, which is 96 indicating that it has a strong preference for certainty and structure. The average score of 70.03 indicates a moderate-to-high level of Uncertainty Avoidance across the seven countries in the sample.

Overall, these statistics illustrate the heterogeneous nature of MENA firms, shaped by country-specific economic conditions, regulatory frameworks, and macroeconomic fluctuations over the 20-year period.

4.2. Inferential statistics

4.2.1. Logistic Regression Results

The logistic regression is conducted to analyze the relationship between corruption and the decision to pay dividends. Corruption measured by the corruption perception index and the decision to pay dividends is a binary value, “1” is assigned for firms that pay dividends and zero is assigned for firms that do not pay dividends.

Table 5. Tests of Model Coefficients

	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step	46.907	12	.000
Block	46.907	12	.000
Model	69.211	13	.000

Corruption as the independent variable and the control variables are included in the model and the results are shown in Table 5. The Chi-square value is 69.2 with significance level of (p-value) of 0.000, which indicates that corruption and the control variables significantly contributes to the model and have a significant effect on the dependent variable (decision to pay dividends).

Table 6. Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	2852.073 ^a	.032	.043

. Estimation terminated at iteration number 3 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001

Table 6 indicates that the independent variable which is the corruption and the firm and country control variables are able to explain the variability of the dependent variable which is the decision to pay dividends by 4.3%.

Table 7. Results of the Hosmer and Lemeshow Test

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	7.179	8	.265

In Table 7, The p-value associated with the Hosmer and Lemeshow test is 0.265 (greater than 0.05), confirming a good model fit, indicating that there is no significant difference between the observed and expected frequencies

Table 8. Variables in the Logistic Regression Equation

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
COI	-.023	.004	34.606	1	.000	.978
PRO	.723	.645	1.258	1	.262	2.061
CAH	-.154	.474	.105	1	.746	.858
FGR	-.010	.018	.323	1	.570	.990
LEV	.347	.336	1.066	1	.302	1.414
SIZ	.109	.057	3.663	1	.056	1.115
ATG	-.887	.254	12.250	1	.000	.412
REA	.262	.180	2.118	1	.146	1.299
SSA	-.415	.362	1.316	1	.251	.660
PMI	-.005	.003	1.991	1	.158	.995
GCI	.001	.005	.022	1	.883	1.001
EGR	.006	.013	.208	1	.649	1.006
UAC	.040	.011	12.851	1	.000	1.040

Table 8, presents the results of the logistic regression for this study. The Wald statistic for corruption is 34.6, with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that corruption is statistically significant in determining whether a firm will pay dividends.

The coefficient for corruption perception index is -0.023. These results show a negative relationship between corruption percentage index and the decision to pay dividends. This means that as corruption decreases (CPI increases, indicating a cleaner country), the decision to pay dividends is less likely to be taken, meaning that corruption positively impacts the decision to pay dividends.

These findings support the study's hypothesis that corruption has a significant positive impact on the decision to pay dividends.

Corruption significantly worsens the agency problem by increasing the agency cost of equity. In corrupt environments, managers, who are responsible for overseeing daily operations, may misuse firm resources to pay bribes to public officials, either for personal gain or to secure short-term advantages for the firm. Such actions often lead to the establishment of direct ties with corrupt government entities, creating opportunities for managers to exploit company resources. As Tran (2020) notes, managers in corrupt settings are better positioned to divert funds through unofficial payments, increasing the risk of shareholder expropriation. In response, shareholders, aware of this potential misuse, have strong incentives to closely monitor managerial behavior. As a mitigation to the agency problem, they often push for higher dividend payouts, to limit the available cash. This pressure for increased dividends serves as a protective mechanism against the expropriation of shareholder wealth, particularly in environments where weak governance and corruption enable managers to act in their own self-interest.

The asset tangibility and national culture show a significant relationship on the decision to pay dividends. While for the rest of the control variables which include the profitability, cash, leverage, firm growth, leverage, firm size, firm maturity, uncertainty, protecting minority index, getting credit, annual GDP growth rate, they show an insignificant relationship with the dividend decision which means that these variables do not have an impact on the company's decision to pay dividends when employing the logistic regression model.

The negative coefficient of -0.887 at a significance level of 0.000 for **asset tangibility** indicates a strong inverse relationship with the decision to pay dividends. Theoretically, this suggests that as asset tangibility increases, the likelihood of paying dividends decreases.

UAC represents **national culture**, measured by the uncertainty avoidance index provided by Hofstede (Hofstede, et al., 2010). The results show a positive significant relationship between uncertainty avoidance and the decision to pay dividends. A high uncertainty avoidance

index, reflects a low tolerance for uncertainty. Accordingly, investors would prefer high dividends as supported by the bird-in-hand theory. (Zheng & Ashraf, 2014)

4.2.2. Weighted Least Square Results

Table 9. Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.303 ^a	.092	.091	.640
2	.521 ^b	.271	.267	.575

a. Predictors: (Constant), IV
 b. Predictors: (Constant), IV, C3, C4, C11, C8, C6, C12, C5, C2, C9, C1, C10, C7

Table 9 shows the model summary of employing the weighted least square regression method. Model 1, includes only the independent variable which is the corruption and it explains 9.2% of the variance in the dependent variable which is the dividend payout ratio. While, model 2, includes the independent variable in addition to the control variables. The results indicate that 27% of the variance in the dividend payout ratio is explained by the model. Indicating that the added variables improve the explanation of the model.

Table 10: Coefficients in the WLS Equation

Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
COI	-0.004	0	-0.197	-9.107	0	-0.004
PRO	0.27	0.053	0.116	5.092	0	0.27
CAH	0.223	0.039	0.109	5.756	0	0.223
FGR	-0.007	0.004	-0.03	-1.701	0.089	-0.007
LEV	0.108	0.084	0.049	1.917	0.038	0.108
SIZ	0.012	0.007	0.167	1.273	0.096	0.012
ATG	-0.099	0.026	-0.072	-3.815	0	-0.099
REA	0.061	0.018	0.127	3.088	0	0.061
SSA	0.047	0.046	0.032	1.311	0.076	0.047
PMI	0	0.001	0.016	0.792	0.428	0
GCI	0.004	0.002	0.11	2.02	0	0.004

EGR	0	0.001	0.006	0.322	0.748	0
UAC	0.006	0.007	0.24	0.618	0.316	0.006

Table 10 presents the results of the weighted least regression for this study. The p-value for corruption is 0.000, indicating that corruption is statistically significant in impacting the dividend payout ratio. The coefficient for corruption is -0.004, suggesting a negative relationship between the corruption perception index (CPI) and the dividend payout ratio. This suggest that as corruption increases (CPI decrease, indicating a corrupted environment), the dividend payout increases. This implies that corruption positively impacts the dividend payout ratio.

The findings from the weighted least squares regression support the study’s hypothesis that corruption has a significant positive impact on the dividend payout ratio.

Corruption exacerbates the agency problem by increasing the agency cost of equity. Managers, who are responsible for overseeing daily business operations, may misuse firm resources to pay bribes to public officials for personal gain, thereby fostering direct ties with corrupt government entities. In some cases, they may also engage in corrupt practices to secure short-term advantages for the firm. Consequently, shareholders have strong incentives to closely monitor managerial behaviour and pressure them to distribute higher dividends as a strategy to mitigate the agency problem. As suggested by Tran (2021) managers in corrupt environments may be better able to exploit the money from their companies due to unofficial payments, and they may seize this chance to expropriate shareholders. Shareholders, on the other hand, often put pressure on managers to increase dividend payments when they recognise this expropriation behaviour.

Profitability, cash, leverage, asset tangibility, firm maturity and creditor protection, show a significant relationship with dividend decision and dividend payout ratio. As for the firm growth rate, firm size, standard deviation (uncertainty), protecting minority index, annual GDP growth rate, and uncertainty avoidance, these variables show an insignificant relationship with the dividend decision and dividend payout which means that these variables do not have an impact on the company’s dividend payout policy.

From Table 10, The coefficient of **profitability** is 0.000 ($p > 0.05$), positive and statistically significant, implying that firms in the MENA region with higher profits will choose to distribute have more dividend payout policies. Empirically, the positive findings are in line with Fama and French (2001). **Cash** has a strong positive association with the decision pay

dividends. The p-value value is 0.223 and 0.000 statistically significant. The positive findings are in line with Ho (2003). Firms with greater cash and cash equivalents will distribute dividends at a higher rate than those with less cash. **Financial leverage** produced positive coefficient of 0.108 at the significant level of .038%, meaning that firms in the MENA region with high financial leverage will have a significant increase in dividend payout. The result is in line with Chang and Rhee (1990) who indicated that firms use debt to distribute dividends. **Asset Tangibility** has a negative coefficient of -.099 for the dividend payout at the significance level of .000. The negative result is consistent with the study of Aivazian et al., (2003), who argue that firms operating in developing economies having a lot of physical assets typically pay out smaller dividends. The results of the regression analysis show a strong positive significant relationship between **firm maturity** and the dividend payout, these findings confirm the life cycle theory developed by Grullon et al (2002), when firms are more mature; they tend to pay more dividends. The results show a strong positive significant relationship between **getting credit** and the dividend pay-out, with coefficient of 0.004 at the significant level of 0.000. Managers compensate for weak creditor rights by paying low dividends. (Unlu & Brockman, 2009).

5. Conclusion

The existing literature suggests that corruption can be “grease in the wheels” or “sand in the wheels. Several prior studies have focused on the impact of corruption at the macro level and very few studies examine its impact at the micro level. (Donadelli et al., 2014). The scarcity of research was noted in Svensson (2003) who wrote, “Despite more than two decades of research, however, economic studies on corruption at the firm level are rather limited.” Additionally, some recent incidents of corruption in the MENA region have attracted much attention; a large part of the MENA region has witnessed multiple social upheavals. The standard literature, surveys and perception indexes also indicate that corruption is widespread in the MENA region. It is argued that corruption may increase the agency cost of equity and hence shareholders have high incentives to force managers to pay dividends as a mechanism to reduce agency costs and to limit the excessive cash. This study aims to examine the effect of corruption on the dividend decision in light of the agency theory in seven selected countries in the MENA region. It is been found that corruption is positively related to both the decision to pay dividends and the dividend payout ratio in stock listed firms in seven selected MENA countries. Corruption worsens the agency problem by raising agency costs, as managers may

misuse firm resources for personal gain or short-term advantages. This incentivizes shareholders to closely monitor management and push for higher dividends to limit expropriation.

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